

worm

Waste in humanitarian Operations:
Reduction and Minimisation

D8.2. Final report on dissemination,
communication, and exploitation

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

ACRONYM	FULL NAME
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
ECHO	European Civil protection and Humanitarian aid Operations
EIP-AGRI	European Innovation Partnership for agricultural productivity and sustainability
EMT	Emergency Medical Teams
FRC	Finnish Red Cross
HO	Humanitarian Organisations
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KLU	Kühne Logistics University
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
NGOs	Non-Governmental Organisations
PSA	Pamela Steele Associates
SOP	Standard Operating Procedure
VNRC	Vietnamese Red Cross
WPs	Work Packages

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BACKGROUND ABOUT WORM

WORM aims to design guidelines and support actions for circular economy in the humanitarian sector. It integrates bio-based technological solutions, leverages procurement for waste reduction, improves waste management methods and prioritises the sustainable livelihoods of waste pickers. WORM focuses on two selected settings: field hospital deployments and humanitarian livelihood programmes with a waste picking component. Following a collaborative and multi-actor approach, WORM brings together medical and humanitarian organisations, procurement service providers, logistics providers, waste management services and academic partners.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document is a deliverable of the WORM Project, funded under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 101135392.

The document is drafted by Euronovia (WP7/8 leader), with inputs from all partners.

This deliverable is the final report on communication and dissemination, produced as part of Work Package 8 on communication, dissemination and exploitation, whose objectives are to:

- Ensure maximum visibility of the project through tailored communication activities in order to raise awareness about the potential of WORM and reach out to society and show its impact and benefits.
- Disseminate to the target groups the aim of WORM, the activities carried out in the project, the available outputs, as well as the knowledge created.
- Promote open access and re-use of data used by WORM.
- Run a local awareness campaign in the community to ensure the proper treatment of especially medical waste.

The scope of this document is to summarise and analyse the communication tools created, and dissemination activities performed during the WORM project; the outreach of the communication channels and tools; and the evaluation of performance and impact of these actions and tools, based on pre-established Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).

Several communication resources and tools were developed for WORM at its launch: Euronovia created a unique project logo and the accompanying brand guidelines, as well as templates and tools to support partners to promote the project in a consistent and efficient manner: PowerPoint presentation, and deliverable templates on Word, the project flyer, roll-up banner, and poster, as well as the public project website, and social media (LinkedIn, Twitter and Facebook). In the second half of the project, a presentation video, final brochure and media press kit were created. PSA and VNRC also produced targeted and context-based materials to support the key messages of the local awareness campaigns.

To achieve a greater impact, partners were regularly invited to share project results and information in their own communication channels and through their existing networks. Great efforts were made by everybody to ensure appropriate visibility of the project and dissemination of results over the course of the project. To keep track of all communication and dissemination actions, a collaborative spreadsheet was created and made available by Euronovia on the SharePoint area of the project since M1 and was regularly updated by partners. This internal tool has been used to monitor and evaluate the dissemination and communication actions undertaken by the consortium during the 24 months of the project.

The outcomes of this evaluation process show that a high number of communication and dissemination activities were performed by all partners. These include a significant use of social media, organisation of

and participation in online and face-to-face events and workshops, online articles, newsletters and more, as detailed in the next sections of this report.

An analysis of the impact of these actions using KPIs is presented in the Section 5 of this report.

NON-TECHNICAL SUMMARY

This is WORM's project Final Report on Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation. This deliverable summarizes the dissemination and communication activities related to project activities and results carried out by WORM partners during the 24 months of the project.

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE DECLARATION

The authors of this deliverable declare that generative Artificial Intelligence was only used as a support tool and that the results have been cross-checked, discussed and interpreted by the authors themselves.

1. DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION STRATEGY

The planning and execution of the project communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities require a schedule closely aligned with key project deliverables, milestones, and activities. In this framework, **our activities are organised around 3 phases:**

- **Phase 1 on the prioritisation of product groups** (M1-M6), we prepared a comprehensive communication strategy outlining key messages, target audiences and the selection of appropriate communication channels. During this phase we developed the project website and various communication and dissemination materials, including the project graphical identity (i.e., project logo, branding guidelines, templates for project documents and presentations). In this phase, we drafted the Plan for dissemination, communication, and exploitation (D7.1). At the end of the initial phase, we disseminated the results of the scoping exercise of commonly used product groups that could qualify for seeking bio-based alternative solutions. 5 group products were identified and selected by the consortium for their particular relevance.
- **Phase 2 related to the evaluation of bio-based alternatives and local waste management innovation** (M6-M12) focused on deploying specific communication and dissemination activities tailored to the unique characteristics of each Work Packages. In this phase, we drafted the batch #1 of practice abstracts (D7.2) and the mid-report on dissemination, communication, and exploitation activities (D7.3). Dissemination focused on the sustainability assessment of bio-based solutions to be integrated into procurement processes. Workshops and webinars were also organised on the sustainability aspect and the local innovations in waste management. This mainly concerned technical Work packages 1, 2, 3 and 4. A first policy brief on the sustainability criteria (D2.1) was published and clustering activities with the sister project Bio4HUMAN and consortium networks took place.
- **Phase 3 focused on policy recommendations and local implementation** (M13-M24) concentrated on presented of project results, impact assessment, and the dissemination of comprehensive policy brief on waste management in humanitarian sector. Particular focus was given to the target local awareness campaign in Kenya and Vietnam to disseminate and support the implementation of improved waste management. During the final phase, we also focused on the dissemination of WP5 “Recycling and waste management at field hospitals” and WP6 results “Mitigation and livelihoods”. We shared our policy recommendations and results, including the Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) for Emergency Medical Teams (EMTs) and field hospitals as well as the trade-offs involved in introducing bio-based solutions in the humanitarian context. This phase also included drafting the batch #2 of practice abstracts (D8.1) and the final report on dissemination, communication, and exploitation activities (D8.2).

1.1. PURPOSE OF THE COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION ACTIONS

The main purposes of the communication and dissemination activities of the project have been defined as follow:

- Building widespread awareness about the project, its goals, and the importance of waste management challenges in humanitarian operations among the target audiences (see D7.1, section 3.2).

- Raising awareness about the potential of WORM and reach out to society and show its impact and benefits.
- Promoting behaviour change and encouraging the adoption of responsible practices such as waste reduction, reuse, and recycling among humanitarian organisations.
- Highlighting and showcasing the successful outcomes of WORM.
- Engaging with relevant stakeholders including local communities, NGOs, collaboratively address waste management challenges and fostering partnerships and synergies to enhance waste management practices.
- Running a local awareness campaign in the community to ensure the proper treatment of waste, esp. medical waste.
- Showing how European collaboration has achieved more than would have otherwise been possible, notably in fostering citizen engagement through a project-based approach and contributing solving societal and environmental challenges.
- Disseminating best practices/guidance and making better use of WORM results, by ensuring they are taken up by decision-makers to influence policymaking and ensure a follow-up of the development of specific policies related to waste management in humanitarian operations.

The different communication tools and dissemination activities created and implemented during the life of the project are presented below.

2. COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

2.1. BRANDING

The project branding was developed at the beginning of the project to help all partners communicate about WORM in a uniform, consistent, and professional manner. The project logo, project identity, and templates for Word and PowerPoint were designed shortly after the launch of the project.

2.1.1. Logo and project identity

The **WORM logotype** consists of a declination of greens to fit with the “greening the humanitarian sector” objective of the project. This logo is oriented towards the circular economy, as the circularity is represented with the O. We can also find a leaf in the O. A worm is crossing the letters but in a subtle manner. The typography is both rounded and serious. This logo has been chosen for its modernity, movement, and match with the missions of the project.

Figure 1: WORM project logo

The **main font** is ITC Avant Garde which matches well with the logotype and gives a sense of fluidity, connecting with the idea of a worm. The secondary font is Arial.

Specific guidelines on how to use the logo both on a white and dark background, as well as indications on its placement, font and colours are described in its **brand manual** (available to the EC upon request).

The different versions of the project logo as well as the brand manual are available for download on the project management platform.

2.1.2. Templates

Templates for the project deliverables, minutes of meetings, and PowerPoint presentations were created to be used by the partners for all presentations on WORM both in internal and external events.

Figure 2: WORM templates

2.2. E-PRINTED COMMUNICATION MATERIAL

During the first three months of the project, the project description, leaflet and roll-up banner were prepared and distributed to partners to ensure effective communication and raise public awareness of the project. These communication materials were used by partners to promote the project and its early results at events in which they participated. In the last months of the project, a final brochure was designed to showcase the outcomes. It was distributed widely during the final event and is also available to download online.

2.2.1. One-page project description

A **one-page project description** was created for distribution to participants in any project-related activity. This document contains a simple description of the WORM project and its objectives. The design follows the WORM visual identity and is consistent with the other communication materials developed within the communication package. It is available for download on the project website.

Figure 3: WORM one-page project description

2.2.2. Leaflets

A project leaflet with general information on the project was created at M3 (March 2024). It's been distributed to partners for use at any external events that the consortium organised or attended. It is also available for download on the project website.

Figure 4: WORM leaflet

2.2.3. Roll-up

A **roll-up** was created using the project’s visual identity and the same graphical elements used in other communication tools. The text content of the roll-up was kept to a minimum as its main functions is the easy recognition of the project during events. This roll-up has been used during internal and external events attended by the consortium to promote and present the project.

Figure 5: WORM roll-up

2.2.4. Final brochure

A **final brochure** was created at M22 by Euronovia to present the main achievements of WORM. Designed both for specialists and non-specialists, it follows the WORM visual identity. It focuses on the policy briefs developed by the partners, the local awareness campaigns and provides key numbers and information about the project. The brochure was shared via the website, social media, and the final newsletter. Printed versions were distributed at the WORM final event in November 2025.

Figure 6: Cover and inside pages of the WORM final brochure

2.3. WEBSITES

2.3.1. WORM website

The **official website** was launched in April 2024 (M4) at the following address: <https://wormproject.eu>. It was of crucial importance to enhance the visibility of WORM as it served as the main communication tool for the wide dissemination of the project activities, deliverables, and outcomes.

It was kept regularly updated, with new content regarding the events, deliverables, and other resources. In total at M24, 51 news have been published on the WORM website.

Figure 7: WORM website homepage

The impact of the website is monitored using Google Analytics. In the period from 05/04/2024 to 18/12/2025, the website was viewed 5718 times by 1031 users, with an average visit duration of 3'00 minutes.

The website received an excellent worldwide coverage, with visitors spread over all continents (60 countries mapped), demonstrating a global interest in the project outside of the consortium. The top 10 countries of origin of the website's visitors are: United States, Finland, France, Vietnam, United-Kingdom, Kenya, Switzerland, Germany, Italy and Norway.

Figure 8: WORM website coverage

The partners were also promoting the project on their own institutional website. Throughout the lifetime of the project, 51 news articles were published to promote WORM.

2.3.2. WORM Catalogue

The **WORM Catalogue** on bio-based solutions was launched in October 2024 (M10) at the following address: <https://worm.solvoz.com/>. It is also directly accessible via the WORM official website using the button in the header.

It offers an open-access knowledge portal with a catalogue that provides key stakeholders with a transparent, knowledge-driven marketplace for bio-based products and alternatives. It also offers an integrated, comprehensive market assessment tool designed specifically to support humanitarian organisations, health workers and sustainability experts.

By the end of the project, the Catalogue had collected details of 41 bio-based products, organised into the 5 identified WORM priority product groups: Personal Protective Equipment, Syringes and needles, Sharps container, Body bags, and Temporary water bladders.

In the period from 01/10/2024 to 02/11/2025, the WORM Catalogue was viewed 10 427 times by 3 052 users.

Figure 9: WORM Catalogue homepage

2.4. SOCIAL MEDIA

2.4.1. WORM accounts

At the start of the project, three social media accounts were opened for WORM: a [LinkedIn page](#), a [Twitter account](#), and a [Facebook page](#).

- The [LinkedIn page](#) was managed by Euronovia with the aim to disseminate official project information among a professional audience. Partners regularly shared posts on LinkedIn using their personal or institutional LinkedIn accounts, raising awareness of the project among their contact networks. The consortium benefits from the partners' combined networks to reach a wider audience. At M24, the account has 831 followers with 82 907 impressions and 189 posts.
- The [Twitter account](#) was managed by Euronovia, in a more informal way, to keep the followers updated on the work undertaken daily by each partner. The account gathered 32 followers, however, due to the instability and lack of moderation on the platform, the consortium decided to archive the WORM account at M13. The evolving dynamics of X no longer reflected our vision for engaging with our community and driving change towards a more sustainable humanitarian sector. We therefore believed that LinkedIn and Facebook were more effective ways of engaging with our audience and strengthening our shared mission of creating a lasting impact.
- The [Facebook page](#) was managed by Euronovia who feed it by reposting relevant LinkedIn publications. At M24, the account has 40 followers. This platform allowed us to reach our target including the general public, especially during the local campaigns in Kenya and Vietnam.

The audiences on LinkedIn and Facebook differ significantly. LinkedIn is more oriented toward the research community, European stakeholders, and professional networks, while Facebook reaches more local communities and people on the field, especially in Vietnam and Kenya, where users are extremely active.

Figure 10: WORM LinkedIn page

Figure 11: WORM Facebook page

The content shared on the WORM accounts was a mix of project level (e.g., event, deliverables) and local news from the partners (e.g., participation in event), as well as more generic information on WORM’s topics of interest (e.g., waste management, circular economy, humanitarian operations).

The WORM social media accounts were contributing to developing a community of people interested in how the project was going to tackle waste management in humanitarian operations, to raise awareness on the project and its objectives and to allow for more interaction with related initiatives.

The impact of these tools was being monitored monthly through the tools listed below in order to identify the best performing content both in terms of impressions and engagement:

- The impact of the LinkedIn page is accessible by the group administrators.
- Facebook provides useful information on how the content is resonating with the audience, how the page is growing and performing.

The KPIs analysis, included those related to social media, is available in Section 5. A more detailed impact analysis by month (page views, clicks, impressions, etc.) for each social media channel is available upon request to Euronovia.

2.4.2. WORM promotion on partners social media

The partners were also promoting the project on their own institutional and personal social media accounts. Throughout the 24 months of the project, the consortium published 110 publications promoting WORM on LinkedIn and Twitter, reaching more than 43,000 followers.

Solvoyz 4155 abonnés
1 sem. •

This week, we joined with our partners and peers at the final General Assembly and End Conference of the [WORM - Waste management challenges in humanitarian operations](#), hosted at the [Hanken School of Economics in Helsinki \(HUMLOG Institute\)](#), Finland.

On November 3, consortium members gathered for the General Assembly to review progress, align on final deliverables, and discuss the last milestones as we approach the project's close. We're deeply thankful to all partners for the inspiring collaboration and shared commitment throughout this journey.

On November 4, during a packed conference at Hanken, our CEO [Claire Barnhoorn](#) joined the panel discussion reflecting on the project's outcomes and future implications for the humanitarian and development sectors; emphasizing how procurement stands as the key gatekeeper for building more sustainable and resilient humanitarian responses.

A big thank you to the organizers, speakers, and partners for two days of rich dialogue, insights and way forward. [KLU Kühne Logistics University](#), [Humanitarian Innovation Programme](#), [Finnish Red Cross - Suomen Punainen Risti](#), [RMIT University Vietnam](#), [Innovasjon Norge](#), [Pamela Steele Associates](#), [Hoi Chu Thap Do Viet Nam Association](#), [International Medical Corps Croatia](#), [Euronovia](#), [Gyöngyi Kovács](#)

#HorizonEurope #Sustainability #Procurement #Solvoyz #CircularEconomy

Pamela Steele Associates 8 mois •

Join the conversation on waste management in emergency settings! 🌱

WORM Project, invites you to share your expertise on waste management practices in field hospitals and EMTs. Participate in the survey and attend the upcoming workshop to exchange ideas and solutions.

📅 When: 5 March 2025 | 🕒 10:00-12:00 (UK time) | 🌐 Online
🔗 Complete the survey & register for the workshop: <https://lnkd.in/ennskPuN>

Let's work together to improve emergency response sustainability!

Afficher la traduction

HUMLOG Institute 2325 abonnés
9 mois • Modifié •

Join us at #HNPW on March 24th at 16:00 for an info session on the WORM project!

This session provides an update on the [WORM - Waste management challenges in humanitarian operations](#) project, focusing on progress in waste reduction within humanitarian operations. It will cover recent achievements, challenges, and future plans, offering insights into strategies for minimizing waste and enhancing sustainability in humanitarian efforts.

📅 Register here for the session: <https://lnkd.in/d45-WdGc>
🌐 See more of the HUMLOG Institute's sessions here: <https://lnkd.in/d9q26raA>

#humlog #wormeuproject #wastemanagement #humanitarian #circulareconomy #fieldhospitals #environment

Afficher la traduction

Figure 12: Promotion of WORM on partners social media

This wide dissemination of the project by the partners to their various networks contributed to the successful achievement of the WORM social media KPIs in just 24 months. In fact, the target was 500 followers by the end of the project, and we are currently at 871. This demonstrates the effectiveness and relevance of the communication and dissemination activities carried out by the consortium.

2.5. AUDIOVISUAL MATERIALS

Several videos were produced and posted online to ensure visibility of the project and its activities:

- **WORM interview series:** Interviews with WORM partners were recorded during events, edited by Euronovia and then published. 17 interviews of the consortium were posted, with a total of 581 views:
 - [Gyöngyi Kovács](#), WORM coordinator (Hanken).
 - [Virva Tuomala](#) (Hanken).
 - [Margot Rocheteau](#) (Hanken).
 - [Sarah Joseph](#) (KLU).
 - [Seng Kiong Kok](#) (RMIT).
 - [Trinh Duc Tran](#) (RMIT).
 - [Syed Yasir Ahmad](#) (IMC).
 - [Hoa Nguyen](#) (VNRC).
 - [Claire Barnhoorn](#) (Solvoyz).
 - [Ville Juusela](#) (Finnish Red Cross).
 - [Therese Marie Uppström Pankratov](#) (Innovasjon Norge).
 - [Maria Besiou](#) (KLU).
 - [Pamela Steele](#) (Pamela Steele Associates).
 - [Hellen Wanza](#) (Pamela Steele Associates).
 - [Lucie Guilloteau](#) (Euronovia).
 - [Anaïs Loudières](#) (Euronovia).
 - And a final interview of [Gyöngyi Kovács](#) (Hanken).

- **WORM promotional videos:** Videos were designed and published to promote:
 - The participation of [WORM at the HNPW2024](#) (with a total of 45 views).
 - The [WORM consortium meeting](#) in Vietnam (with a total of 48 views).
 - The WORM Bio-based Solutions [Catalogue](#) (with a total of 42 views).
 - The project [presentation video](#) (with a total of 277 views).
 - The WORM local awareness campaign in Vietnam through 2 videos (with a total of 365)
 - Launch of the local awareness campaign in [Thai Nguyen Province](#)
 - Launch of the local awareness campaign in [Khanh Hoa Province](#)
 - The WORM [local awareness campaign in Kenya](#) (with a total of 164 views)
 - The participation of [WORM at the HNPW2025](#) (with a total of 139 views)
 - And the WORM [Final event](#) in Helsinki (with a total of 152 views)

- **WORM webinars & workshops.**

To gather all these different project videos in one place, a WORM [YouTube channel \(@WORM_EUproject\)](#) was created in April 2024 (M4). At M24, this YouTube channel contains 32 videos obtaining more than 1,400 views and 23 subscribers. This YouTube channel was regularly updated with videos throughout the project's lifetime, reflecting ongoing activities, interviews, and news updates.

2.6. NEWSLETTERS

At M24, 4 **newsletters** and 1 **mailing** were sent out to our ever-growing subscribers list (258 subscribers as of December 2025). The newsletters were published regularly every 6 months and included the latest project news with links to the website in order to drive more traffic. A dedicated newsletter was created for the Final Event, presenting the key information (date, venue, and programme) along with a registration button. This helped us reach an even broader audience and resulted in more than 40 online attendees for our final event.

All newsletters as well as the mailing were made available on the project website and are disseminated through all social media platforms.

- [Newsletter 1](#): June 2024
- [Newsletter 2](#): December 2024 (joint with Bio4HUMAN)
- [Newsletter 3](#): June 2025
- [Mailing – WORM final event](#): September 2025
- [Newsletter 4](#): December 2025

On average, the opening rate for the WORM newsletter is 50% and the click rate 38%.

Figure 13: Screenshot of WORM third newsletter

The partners also sent out newsletters to their networks to promote the WORM project. At M24, the consortium sent out 14 newsletters. These reached 1,584 subscribers.

2.7. PRESS RELATIONS

Important efforts were dedicated to press relations to ensure a good media coverage about the WORM activities, especially the local awareness campaign. In total, 5 press releases were published during the life of the project and distributed by the consortium to their contact networks. They can be downloaded from [the project website](#) in a dedicated webpage.

- A first [press release](#) was drafted by Solvoz in October 2024 to officially announce the launch of the WORM Catalogue on Bio-Based Solutions. This press release, originally in English, was translated into French, Finnish, and Swedish. Following the distribution of the press release, an article was published in a non-scientific media, the [Helsinki Times](#).
- A second [press release](#) was prepared in English by Pamela Steele Associates (PSA) in February 2025 to officially launch the innovative waste management campaign conducted in Kisumu, Kenya. Following its distribution and the first results of the campaign, a short report was featured on the Kenyan TV show [Citizen TV Kenya](#).
- A third [press release](#) was drafted in English and Vietnamese by the Vietnam Red Cross Society (VNRC) in March 2025. The objective was to provide information about the launch of a comprehensive waste management campaign in Dinh Hoa District, Thai Nguyen Province, Vietnam, which was to take place on 18–19 March 2025. This activity had a significant local impact, with four articles published in the press ([THAI NGUYEN NEWS](#), [BAOMOI](#), [Tra Cứu Quy Hoach](#), [THAI NGUYEN PORTAL](#)) and two reports on local TV ([Thai Nguyen TV](#), [Dinh Hoa district TV](#)).
- A fourth [press release](#) was prepared in English by VNRC in July 2025 to promote the organisation of the “*Together with Waste Collectors – Connecting Communities, Protecting the Environment*”

event which was organised in the Nam Ninh Hoa city, Khanh Hoa province, Vietnam. Following the distribution of the press release, two articles were published in local media ([Khanh Hoa Online](#), [VTV News](#)) and one report was featured on the [QPVN TV](#), a Vietnam national TV show.

Figure 14: Articles in the Helsinki Times, the Thai Nguyen and the Khanh Hoa online.

Figure 15: Screenshot of national TV reports about WORM local awareness campaigns

- A **final media press kit** was created in December 2025 by Euronovia with contributions from all the project partners. Targeting both specialists and non-specialists, especially the humanitarian & medical organisations, the media and the general public, it consists of 20 pages focusing on the project's main achievements, the local awareness campaigns, and WORM's wider impact. The press kit was distributed via the website, social media and the final newsletter. It was also made available to the consortium for local distribution.

Figure 16: Cover page of the final media press kit

3. DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

3.1. DELIVERABLES

All **WORM public deliverables** are accessible through the project’s website (<https://wormproject.eu/delivrables/>). The WORM project has an Open access policy and is oriented towards the sharing of the results to various stakeholders, as almost all deliverables are public (23/27 deliverables).

Figure 17: WORM deliverables page on the website

3.2. ORGANISATION OF EVENTS

During the project duration, partners have organised several types of events for communication and dissemination purposes, as detailed below.

3.2.1. Workshops

At the end of the project, we have organised 10 workshops. These are:

- WORM workshop at the HNPW2024**

Figure 18: WORM session at the HNPW2024

The **WORM interactive session** took place during the Humanitarian Networks and Partnerships Weeks (HNPW) 2024 at the International Conference Centre in Geneva (Switzerland) on Wednesday afternoon, 8 May 2024. The aim was to inform stakeholders about WORM's objectives and activities and to receive their input on product groups, the plug-and-play framework with different scenarios and criteria to identify the most appropriate waste management technology. 44 participants attended this hybrid face-to-face and online event.

- **WORM workshop on Promoting Sustainability through Humanitarian Procurement: Development of a sustainability criteria framework.**

Co-organised by WORM and DG ECHO (European Civil Protection and Humanitarian Aid Operations), this **workshop** took place online on 25 June 2024. The aim was to lay the foundations for developing actionable recommendations for embedding sustainability in humanitarian procurement processes. 48 participants joined this online event.

- **WORM workshops in Kenya**

Partners have also organised **workshops** locally to engage the local and regional humanitarian community:

- [Validation and Co-creation Workshop](#) "Medical Waste Management: An Overview of existing Disinfection Methods" organised by PSA the 26-27 September 2024 at Kisumu (Kenya) and attended by 22 participants.
- [Online Validation and co-creation Workshop](#) "Medical Waste Management: An Overview of existing Disinfection Methods" organised online by PSA the 3 October 2024 and attended by 11 participants.

Figure 19: PSA face-to-face workshop in Kisumu

- **WORM workshop in Vietnam**

This **workshop** took place at the Saigon Campus of RMIT University the 8 October 2024. The aim was to inform them about WORM's objectives and activities and then to receive their input in parallel sessions on Vietnam's informal waste management sector and waste management in a field hospital. At the same time, the plug and play models developed by the project as a decision support tool were tested live the WORM Catalogue was officially launch. 60 participants attended this face-to-face event

Figure 20: WORM workshop in Vietnam

□ **WORM workshop on waste management adopted by emergency medical teams and field hospitals in emergency responses**

This **workshop**, which took place online on 5 March 2025, was co-organised by IMC Croatia, FRC, ICRC and PSA. The aim was to emphasise the importance of collaboration among emergency medical teams to improve sustainability and environmental responsibility. It provided a valuable platform for exchanging ideas on enhancing medical waste management in emergency situations. The event concluded with a breakout exercise to gather feedback from participants on the development of standard operating procedures for emergency waste management. 44 participants attended this online workshop and the [video recording](#) on YouTube has 55 views.

□ **WORM & Bio4HUMAN workshop at HNPW2025**

Co-organised by WORM and Bio4HUMAN, the **session** on “Waste management in humanitarian operations: Bio-based solutions and raising awareness challenge” took place during the Humanitarian Networks and Partnerships Weeks (HNPW) 2025 at the International Conference Centre in Geneva (Switzerland) on Monday 24 March 2025. The aim was to provide update on the WORM and Bio4HUMAN projects, focusing on progress in waste reduction within humanitarian operations and discussing recent achievements, challenges, and future plans. 18 participants attended this hybrid event and the [video recording](#) on YouTube has 44 views.

□ **WORM workshop at the AidEx Conference 2025 in Kenya**

The WORM **participative session** on “Sustainable Livelihoods for Informal Waste Pickers and Innovative Business Models” took place on Wednesday 11 June 2025, at the Safari Park Hotel in Nairobi during the AidEx Nairobi Conference. The session focused on identifying social, economic, and environmental risks and opportunities for waste pickers, as well as exploring circular economy models and inclusive strategies tailored to the Kenyan context. The Kenya National Wastepickers Association Welfare Association participated in the workshop, providing insights into the unique challenges of the Nakuru landfill and its community-led advocacy successes. 25 participants attended this face-to-face event.

Figure 21: WORM session at AidEx Nairobi 2025

□ **WORM workshop on trade-offs in bio-based materials.**

This **validation workshop** was organised online and took place the 9 September 2025. The aim of this interactive event was to review the assumptions regarding trade-offs in bio-based materials to ensure that they truly reflect real-world conditions. 10 participants attended this online event.

□ **WORM workshop on the dangers of incinerating mixed medical waste**

This **virtual workshop** took place online on 16 September 2025. It focused on the significant health and environmental risks associated with incineration while exploring safer and more sustainable alternatives for waste treatment. Building on the **awareness campaign** carried out in Kisumu, Kenya, the workshop brought together experts, practitioners, and stakeholders from across the health, environment, and humanitarian fields to strengthen dialogue and collaboration around responsible medical waste management. 37 participants attended this online event and the [video recording](#) on YouTube has 10 views.

3.2.2. Webinars

During the project duration, we have organised the following 3 **webinars**. These are:

- Greening the Humanitarian sector through Innovation Friendly Procurement | 25 June 2024 | Innovasjon Norge. 32 participants joined the webinar and the [video recording](#) on YouTube has 74 views.
- Strengthening medical waste management systems to reduce the environmental impact of humanitarian operations | 17 September 2024 | Solvoz. 45 participants joined the webinar and the [video recording](#) on YouTube has 91 views.
- Waste Management in Humanitarian Field Hospitals | 5 June 2025 | Solvoz, IMC Croatia and FRC. 28 participants joined the webinar and the presentations are available on the [WORM website](#). The webinar presented an evidence-based overview of waste management challenges and opportunities in humanitarian field hospitals, highlighting major health risks, weak early-response waste data and the need for far stronger coordination across agencies. It reviewed a two-year feasibility study on gasification, concluding that although the technology shows long-term promise, it is not yet suitable for rapid emergency deployment. Findings from technical, social, and waste-stream analyses stressed that better segregation, the early establishment of simple materials recovery facilities, and meaningful engagement with existing recyclers and waste pickers are essential to avoid harm. Case examples from Japan and Finland demonstrated structured, practical models for safe handling, consolidation and monitoring. The webinar closed with an integrated waste management framework tailored for Emergency Medical Teams, emphasising planning, preparation, execution, and environmentally responsible practices, supported by clear tools, guidance, and national compliance requirements.

Figure 22: Screenshots of WORM webinars

3.2.3. Targeted local awareness campaigns

Targeted and dedicated awareness-raising campaigns (T8.3) that engaged local communities were organised and implemented during the second year of the project (M13–M24). Activities were carried out in Kenya (in Kisumu County by PSA) and Vietnam (in Thai Nguyen and Khanh Hoa provinces by VNRC).

With the support of other end-users in the consortium (ACF, CRS, ICRC and IMC), VNRC and PSA also developed relevant materials to help local communities with waste management.

These campaigns aimed to advocate for, and raise awareness of, improved waste management practices in specific local contexts. In total, WORM carried out 4 targeted, community-based campaigns in Kenya and Vietnam, reaching over 4 200 people.

□ **Campaigns in Kenya**

From January to September 2025, PSA conducted **an awareness campaign** in Kisumu County, Kenya, to inform local communities, healthcare professionals, young people and key stakeholders about the environmental and health risks associated with poor waste management methods. On 5 June 2025, the World Environment Day Celebration served as a flagship event, ensuring maximum public participation and broader dissemination.

▪ **The campaign in Kisumu County**

In order to boost community engagement, PSA collaborated with Misango Arts Ensemble, a renowned local youth arts group based in Kisumu that is recognised for using theatre and the arts to drive social change. This collaboration was at the heart of the campaign's artistic and community engagement strategy.

At the start of the campaign, PSA obtained a permission letter from the Kisumu County Health Minister's office, authorising the **creation of murals within healthcare facilities**. Misango Arts Ensemble's unemployed youth artists were commissioned to create impactful painted murals in three healthcare facilities in Kisumu County, with the aim of reinforcing the campaign's message. These facilities were Jaramogi Oginga Odinga Teaching and Referral Hospital, Kisumu County Referral Hospital, and Lumumba Sub-County Hospital.

Created between April and June 2025, the murals depicted the segregation of medical waste, the harmful impacts of incineration and protective practices for workers and the environment. They also depicted the lifecycle of waste, from generation to disposal, and provided visual guidance on safer alternatives, such as autoclaving, segregation, sanitary landfills and chemical disinfection. The murals leave a lasting impression and create community reference points. They visually convey the dangers of incineration, emphasise the importance of waste segregation and promote safer alternatives, serving as continuous educational tools. [A video](#) about the murals and its messages is available on WORM YouTube channel.

Figure 23: the murals in the 3 healthcare facilities

To conclude the campaign, a large **stakeholder’s workshop** was held on 16 September 2025, bringing together a wider audience of policymakers, healthcare officials, NGO representatives, environmental experts, community leaders and private sector representatives. The workshop aimed to educate attendees further on the dangers of incinerating mixed waste and to encourage collective exploration and commitment to sustainable waste management solutions.

▪ The World Environmental Day in Kisumu County

The Misango Arts Ensemble’s artists developed and performed on World Environmental Day 2025 an original, comprehensive and compelling **poem and drama piece**. The performance showcased the effects of toxic emissions from healthcare waste incinerators. The poetry piece reflected on the health and environmental burden of unsustainable waste practices. The performance used artistic expression to educate the public about the hazards of incineration and alternative solutions in an engaging and culturally relevant manner. This approach leveraged local talent, making the message more accessible and memorable. The performance also resonated well with the World Environment Day 2025’s theme of beating plastic pollution.

Figure 24: the artists during the drama piece about the dangers of incineration

A preview of Misango Arts Ensemble’s performance was held on 31 May 2025, at the Mama Grace Onyango Social Hall, specifically targeting key influencers and decision-makers. This pre-event engagement ensured buy-in and awareness among key stakeholders. This session was attended by university students, healthcare professionals who are direct beneficiaries of improved waste management, and representatives from the National Environment Management Authority, the primary policy enforcement body in Kenya. This strategic engagement aimed to garner support and informed policy direction and behaviour change.

Figure 25: Youths distributing WORM brochures and pamphlets during the World Environment Day 2025

In order to conduct these campaigns, 10 youths were employed and trained, and 10 healthcare facilities were engaged. At the end, 2 public performances were conducted, 3 murals created, and 3 000 materials distributed, reaching an audience of more than 3 000 individuals.

□ **Campaigns in Vietnam**

In Vietnam, VNRC carried out **2 targeted local campaigns**, one in the Thai Nguyen Province in March 2025 titled *“Raising community awareness on waste management”* and one in the Khanh Hoa Province in July 2025 titled *“Together with waste collectors – Connecting communities, protecting the environment”*.

▪ **The campaign in Thai Nguyen Province**

The *“Raising community awareness on waste management”* campaign took place on 18 and 19 March 2025 at Dinh Hoa Secondary School and Kim Phuong Primary School in Thai Nguyen Province, Vietnam. The campaign, organised by VNRC, sought to drive lasting behavioural changes in waste management practices by targeting schools, which play a crucial role in fostering green models and strengthening environmental protection activities.

Under the slogan *“Green Day – Act for the Environment”*, various activities were organised at the two schools to raise awareness in a fun and engaging way. To encourage student participation, **interactive sessions** and **hands-on initiatives** were organised, including music performances, tree planting, clean-up events, waste collection drives, and exchanging waste for gifts. **Creative competitions** were organised, including debates, drawing contests, video-making contests and writing contests on environmental protection, to make learning more engaging and interactive. Finally, in cooperation with collection and recycling units, recycling points for materials such as plastic, paper, cans and bottles were set up to ensure regular collection within the project’s timeframe depending on the volume of waste in the schools.

Figure 26: Pictures during the clean-up events in the two schools

In parallel, workshops, seminars and lectures were organised in the schools with the participation of environmental experts, local authority representatives, Red Cross staff and volunteers, teachers, students and parents.

On 18 March, a special event was held to celebrate **Global Recycling Day**, where experts in waste management, reduction and recycling provided guidance on proper waste sorting techniques and highlighted the importance of classifying waste at source.

Figure 27: Picture during the Global Recycling Day

A [video](#) about the Thai Nguyen campaign is available on WORM YouTube channel.

More than 900 participants, including teachers and students, took part in promoting community action for sustainable waste management. 32 trees were planted in school grounds, and 8 waste bins were provided and set up in schools. These contributions will enable the schools to continue their sustainability efforts beyond the campaign, thereby fostering long-term environmental awareness and waste management practices. 600 students took part in creative environmental protection contests, such as drawing, video creation and writing. 20 outstanding entries were awarded prizes at the environmental protection competition.

- The campaign in Khanh Hoa Province

In collaboration with the Khanh Hoa Provincial Red Cross and the People's Committee of Nam Ninh Hoa commune, VNRC organised the event *“Together with waste collectors – Connecting communities, protecting the environment”*, which took place in Nam Ninh Hoa, Vietnam, on 29 July 2025.

This campaign aimed to raise community awareness of the role of informal waste collectors in environmental protection and waste reduction, strengthen the connection between communities and waste collectors, promote the *“Live Green – Live Clean”* spirit, and contribute to the protection of coastal ecosystems, adaptation to climate change, and the promotion of sustainable livelihoods.

Through this event, the VNRC aimed to promote humanitarian values, encourage community responsibility, and emphasise the organisation's commitment to supporting sustainable livelihoods, safeguarding the environment, and addressing climate change.

The campaign brought together informal waste collectors, provincial Red Cross volunteers, and local community representatives. Also present were representatives from the Vietnam Red Cross Headquarters, the provincial government, the Department of Agriculture and Environment, volunteers from provincial Women's and Youth Unions, and international partners including RMIT Vietnam and KLU, as well as members of local media agencies, ensuring broad participation from institutional, community, and informational stakeholders.

Key activities included a **talk show** titled *“Listening to the voices of waste collectors”*, which featured first-hand accounts from waste collectors, and a **technical sharing session** on identifying hazardous waste, safe collection practices and waste classification. There was additionally a community commitment signing titled *“Live green – Live clean”* with citizens, volunteers and delegates. The programme also featured the

presentation of 20 gift sets to informal waste collectors, a **beach clean-up** and the **planting of one hectare** of mangrove forest at Bai Trieu.

Figure 28: Pictures during the beach clean-up and the mangrove planting

[A video](#) about the Khanh Hoah campaign is available on WORM YouTube channel, as well as [another video](#) on the VNRC YouTube channel.

The campaign was attended by more than 300 people, including informal waste collectors and local community representatives. 1 hectare of coastal mangrove forest was planted, and 20 gift sets were given to informal waste collectors. Following the event, waste collection in the ocean continued to be organised every weekend until the end of August 2025. A total of 28 tonnes of waste was collected with the help of 900 Red Cross staff and volunteers.

□ **Print materials**

Brochures, pamphlets, and posters were created for the campaigns by PSA and VNRC with the input of the consortium, and especially the end-users' representatives (Action Contre la Faim, Catholic Relief Services, ICRC and IMC).

PSA and VNRC designed and printed visually engaging and easy to understand communication materials:

- **Informative pamphlet** designed by PSA with infographics and detailed information on the types of hazardous medical waste, alternatives to incineration, the hazards of incineration and simple steps for waste segregation, handling and safe disposal at the facility level.
- **Brochure** prepared by PSA for healthcare facilities and the community outlining the dangers of incineration provided more in-depth information on alternative waste treatment technologies (e.g., autoclaving, chemical disinfection, sanitary landfills, microwave with shredder) and best environmental practices.
- **Poster** designed by PSA with clear visuals and concise messages emphasising the dangers of burning waste and the benefits of proper waste management.
- **Leaflet** and **roll-up** of the WORM project were translated into Vietnamese by VNRC and widely distributed.
- **Standees** were created by VNRC to attract the attention of the targeted audience during the campaigns. The **first one** had less text and a round image to appeal to children. The **second one** was prepared to target a more mature audience.
- A **banner** was designed by VNRC to be suspended above the streets to promote the event in Khanh Hoah Province.

Figure 29: first pages of the pamphlets designed by PSA

To ensure maximum outreach, PSA recruited and trained unemployed youth from Kisumu County who distributed pamphlets, posters and brochures in Kisumu County, Kenya. The youth were trained on the content of the materials to ensure they could explain key messages during distribution. Through the campaign in Kenya, 3 000 materials were distributed or displayed in high-traffic community locations, healthcare facilities and during World Environment Day.

In Vietnam, 4 000 leaflets, standees and roll-ups were distributed or displayed in schools and densely populated areas, such as markets, to spread the message of waste management and environmental protection.

3.2.4. Final event

On Tuesday 4 November 2025 (M23), the WORM project held its **final event** titled “*Field-based solutions for managing medical waste*” at the Hanken School of Economics in Helsinki, Finland. This event was an opportunity to showcase WORM’s key results and celebrate its collective achievements.

Over three hours, participants explored WORM’s main findings: from trade-offs and causal loops of bio-based products in field hospitals to new standard operating procedures for emergency medical teams and field hospitals.

Figure 30: Pictures of the final event

We were honoured to welcome inspiring speakers, including Johan von Schreeb, Professor of Global Disaster Medicine at Karolinska Institutet, Syed Yasir Ahmad, Global WASH advisor at International Medical Corps, as well as Mr. Julien Lugwarha from our sister project Bio4HUMAN and Mr. Giulio Pattanaro, our Project Officer. Their insightful contributions brought valuable and complementary perspectives to the project's results.

The event concluded with a panel discussion featuring representatives from PSA, Solvoz, FRC and Euronovia. This interactive session provided a space to reflect on WORM's major achievements through the lens of four different partners, showcasing the project's multidisciplinary nature and the importance of collaborative expertise in achieving sustainable results.

Figure 31: Picture of the panel discussion

Nearly 90 participants attended the final event, with 47 participants in person and 42 participants online. Presentations are available on the [WORM website](#).

3.3. PARTICIPATION IN EVENTS AND CONFERENCES

The consortium participated in several external events for project promotion and dissemination of results, where partners presented the work done within the project:

- **Practitioner events:**
 - Keynote on “Humanitarian Logistics” at the International Conference on Dynamics in Logistics (LDIC) 2024 | 14 February 2024 | Bremen, Germany | by Hanken.
 - Participation at the European Humanitarian Forum 2024 | 18-19 March 2024 | Brussels, Belgium | by Hanken & Solvoz.
 - Booth and session at the Humanitarian Networks and Partnerships Weeks 2024 | 6-10 May 2024 | Geneva, Switzerland & online | by all.
 - Presentation at the Vietnam's National Conference on Disaster Prevention and Response | 9 May 2024 | Da Nang, Vietnam | by RMIT.
 - Keynote on “Supply Chain Resilience Through Different Crises” at the International Conference on Resilient Systems (ICRS) 2024 | 28 August 2024 | Singapore | by Hanken.
 - Keynote on “Tillväxt genom grön omställning” (Economic growth through green transition) at the Toppsemi 2025 | 2 February 2025 | Helsinki | by Hanken.

- Participation at the Health and Humanitarian Logistics (HHL) Annual Conference 2025 | 19-21 February 2025 | Nairobi, Kenya | by PSA.
 - Session at the Humanitarian Networks and Partnerships Weeks 2025 | 24 March 2025 | Geneva, Switzerland & online | by all.
 - Session at the AidEx Nairobi Conference 2025 | 11 June 2025 | Nairobi, Kenya | by all.
 - Session at the AidEx Geneva 2025 | 22 October 2025 | Geneva, Switzerland | by Hanken & ICRC.
- **Academic conferences:**
- Participation at the 34th POMS conference “Building a sustainable, responsible, and resilient global future” | 25-29 April 2024 | Minneapolis, USA | by KLU.
 - Presentation at the 36th NOFOMA conference “Logistics and Supply Chain Management in a Risky and Uncertain World” | 13-14 June 2024 | Stockholm, Sweden | by Hanken.
 - Presentation at the 2024 POMS International Conference “Operations Management and Information Systems in the Age of Analytics” | 24-27 June 2024 | Istanbul, Türkiye | by Hanken.
 - Participation at the 8th EURO HOpe Mini-Conference | 3-4 October 2024 | Madrid, Spain | by KLU.
 - Invited talk on “Human Factors in Humanitarian Logistics - what we know and what we should know” at the Politecnico di Milano | 18 October 2024 | Milano, Italy | by Hanken.
 - Invited talk on “Waste Management in field hospitals” at the Lecture Series of the Research Institute for Supply Chain Management Winter Semester | 28 October 2024 | Vienna, Austria | by Hanken.
 - Presentations at the EurOMA 2025 Conference “Operations Management opening to multi-disciplinarity in a time of grand challenge” | 13-18 June 2025 | Milan, Italy | by Hanken & PSA.
- **Other events:**
- Participation at the Bioeconomy Changemakers Festival “Youth as driver of transformative change” | 13-14 March 2024 | Online | by Hanken & Euronovia.
 - Participation at the “Platform meeting on plastic waste prevention & reuse systems” organised by the LIFE Programme | 10-12 February 2025 | Brussels, Belgium | by Hanken.
 - Thought provocation in the GBSN changemaker series | 25 August 2025 | online | by Hanken.
 - Presentation at Hanken’s SDG week on “sneak peek to sustainability research” | 24 September 2025 | Helsinki, Finland | by Hanken.

Figure 32: WORM participation in external events.

3.4. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS

During the project lifetime, WORM partners contributed to 4 scientific publications:

- Kovacs, G. and Heaslip, G. “Chapter 9: Humanitarian supply chains: challenging the system”, *The Supply Chain: A System in Crisis*, Business 2024, 2024, p.127-133.
- Tuomala, V., and Schiffing, S., Medical waste management: application of circular economy principles in a developing country context. NOFOMA Conference 2024. June 2024. Stockholm, Sweden.
- Rocheteau, M., Schiffing, S., Tuomala, V., and Steele, P., Integrating healthcare waste management in disaster risk reduction strategies. EurOMA Conference 2025. June 2025. Milan, Italy.
- Tuomala, V., and Joseph, S., Bio-based products in humanitarian medical supply chains: supply market intelligence and life cycle assessment. EurOMA Conference 2025. June 2025. Milan, Italy.

All WORM publications have been uploaded on the WORM community in [Zenodo](#) which was set up by Euronovia at the beginning of the project. This repository is used to store all project deliverables, scientific publications and datasets for long-term preservation. By the end of the project, the files had been downloaded 1 938 times and viewed 2 140 times.

Further publications are currently work in progress and/or under review for various scientific journals. Publications will continue to be added to the WORM community on Zenodo as they become available.

3.5. POLICY BRIEFS & STANDARD OPERATING PROCEDURES

3.5.1. Policy briefs

Policy and decisionmakers at local, national, European, and international levels were one of the target groups clearly identified by the consortium to uptake the project’s results and demonstrate their benefits. To do so, the WORM consortium published 5 policy briefs, that are available on the [WORM website](#) through Zenodo and as summaries in the final brochure:

- **Sustainability criteria** (D2.1 - M8)

KLU combined different sustainable procurement frameworks and adapted them for the humanitarian context, in order to assist the development of sustainability criteria (by Solvoz) for the evaluation of product alternatives (including bio-based alternatives) and their circularity for products prioritised Sustainability criteria (D2.1 - M8). This policy brief is available [here](#).

- **Procurement guidelines** (D2.2 - M12)

Based on extant procurement practices of WORM end-users, Solvoz developed humanitarian procurement guidelines to assist the potential of bio-based solutions to be sought and evaluated in comparative bid analyses. This policy brief is available [here](#).

- **Scaling up** (D3.2 - M12)

Innovasjon Norge developed policy recommendations that support the uptake and diffusion of effective business models in humanitarian contexts & that support humanitarian organisations in sourcing/procuring innovative solutions/services/models from the private sector. This policy brief is available [here](#).

- **Plug and play framework** (D4.2 - M12)

RMIT developed a plug and play framework for the easy identification of, and integration with local waste management partners. This policy brief is available [here](#).

- **Medical waste management (D5.3 - M18)**

Considering the need of field hospitals to be able to manage their own waste if local partners are absent or do not have the adequate capacity or waste treatment methods, Solvoz developed waste management guidelines and policy recommendations for field hospitals that consider alternative waste treatment options, and the implementation and use of bio-based solutions. This policy brief is available [here](#).

Given the importance of these policy briefs throughout the project, we ran a global communication campaign to promote the WORM project's recommendations. The aim was to make the policy briefs even more accessible to increase their visibility, encourage broader uptake of the recommendations, and foster continued engagement beyond the project's end.

3.5.2. Standard Operating Procedures

Another important target group for the WORM project is humanitarian & medical organisations. In the second year, two technical documents in the form of Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) were developed to help these organisations with waste management and are available on the [WORM website](#) through Zenodo.

- **SOP for Product Use, Recycling, and Reverse Logistics (D5.1, M24)**

This SOP translates WORM's circular economy principles into actionable guidance for Emergency Medical Teams (EMTs) and field hospitals. It provides standardized procedures for sustainable product use, reuse, repair, recycling, and reverse logistics, ensuring that humanitarian operations minimize waste and environmental impact while maintaining compliance with donor and host-country requirements. The SOP emphasizes life-cycle costing, bio-based procurement, modular infrastructure, and partnerships with local recyclers to embed circularity across the entire product lifecycle. This SOP is available [here](#).

- **SOP for Donation and Handover Management (D5.2, M24)**

This SOP offers a structured, ethical, and transparent framework for the donation and handover of medical and non-medical items by EMTs and field hospitals. It operationalizes circularity principles by promoting reuse, repair, and responsible reverse logistics while preventing environmental burdens on local health systems. The SOP outlines a 10-step donation lifecycle, including feasibility assessments, recipient engagement, documentation, and post-transfer monitoring, ensuring compliance with WHO standards and national regulations. This SOP is available [here](#).

3.6. PRACTICE ABSTRACTS

The [European Innovation Partnership Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability \(EIP-AGRI\) project database](#) showcases innovative projects from across Europe that promote innovation and knowledge exchange for agriculture, forestry and rural areas. A special effort is made to share knowledge and solutions that are ready to be put into practice. To this end, WORM has created its [project profile](#) on the EIP-AGRI Project Database and published [its innovative intermediate and final results](#) in the form of summaries for practitioners in the common EIP-AGRI.

The **first batch of 4 practice abstracts (D7.2)** was delivered at the end of October 2024:

- [Practice #1](#): A plug and play waste management model for humanitarian organisations in diverse settings: A decision-support tool for deployments.
- [Practice #2](#): Greening humanitarian response through innovation friendly procurement.
- [Practice #3](#): Scoping exercise.
- [Practice #4](#): Sustainability in humanitarian procurement.

The **second batch of 8 practice abstracts (D8.1)** was published at the end of July 2025:

- [Practice #5](#): Making circular economy business models work in humanitarian contexts.
- [Practice #6](#): A technical and economic assessment of bio-based alternatives for priority medical supplies for humanitarian use.
- [Practice #7](#): Non-burn disinfection alternatives to improve medical waste management in humanitarian settings.
- [Practice #8](#): Stakeholder engagement workshop and webinar on Waste management practices.
- [Practice #9](#): Life Cycle Assessment of bio-based medical items and cleaner waste solutions for field hospitals.
- [Practice #10](#): Community engagement in humanitarian waste management: Lessons from Vietnam’s WORM Project.
- [Practice #11](#): Community-driven campaigns to raise awareness on medical waste management in Kisumu, Kenya.
- [Practice #12](#): Supply market intelligence with the bio-based solutions catalogue.

Figure 33: WORM project profile on the EIP-AGRI Project Database

3.7. CLUSTERING AND SYNERGIES

As a coordination and support action, the WORM project recognises the key role of clustering activities. Throughout the duration of the project, WORM has strived to maximise its impact by promoting its activities and results, while also improving the efficiency of its actions by learning from the experiences of other organisations. Thus, the WORM consortium has placed particular emphasis on knowledge sharing and networking, seeking to collaborate with individual organisations and experts, as well as with analogous projects with similar funding structures. This collaborative approach aligns with the project’s strategy of leveraging collective expertise and experience to optimise its outcomes.

WORM partners are involved in several European and international humanitarian networks with whom they developed synergies to promote the activities and results of the WORM project, as well as to improve the efficiency of its actions by learning from the experiences of other organisations.

Table 1: List of partners involved in humanitarian networks

Networks	WORM partners
Environmental Sustainability in Humanitarian Logistics project (WREC)	Hanken, KLU, and ICRC
Humanitarian Logistics and Supply Chain Research Institute (HUMLOG Institute)	Hanken
HELP Logistics	Kuhne Logistics University

Humanitarian Innovation Programme	Innovasjon Norge
International Association of Public Health Logisticians (IAPHL), the Humanitarian Logistics Association	Pamela Steele Associates
Humanitarian Environment Network (REH), Humanitarian Logistics (HULO)	Action contre la Faim

The different clustering activities implemented during the project are presented below:

- An online meeting was organised on November 25, 2024, by Bio4HUMAN to discuss circular economy, the challenges of waste management and the development of innovative bio-based solutions. WORM coordinator participated in this event. This meeting gathered several European projects:
 - [Bio4Africa](#) (Horizon 2020, Grant Agreement No. 101000762)
 - [CIRCULAR BIOCARBON](#) (Horizon 2020, Grant Agreement No. 101023280)
 - [ENZYCLE](#) (Horizon 2020, Grand Agreement No. 887913)
 - [PRESERVE](#) (Horizon 2020, Grant Agreement No. 952983)
 - [SynoProtein](#) (Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking, Grant Agreement No. 101112345)
 - [LUCRA](#) (Horizon Europe, Grant Agreement No. 10082169)
 - [HEREWEAR](#) (Horizon 2020, Grant Agreement No. 101000632)
 - [COUNTLESS](#) (Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking, Grant Agreement No. 101112453)
- PSA organised a webinar with the Reproductive Health Supplies on [Strengthening medical waste management systems to reduce the environmental impact of humanitarian operations](#) during which the project was showcased.
- PSA [participated in a webinar](#) hosted by the [Reproductive Health Supplies Coalition](#) titled “Strengthening Medical Waste Management Systems to Reduce the Environmental Impact of Humanitarian Operations” on 17 September 2024. The session disseminated WORM project findings and facilitated knowledge exchange with a global community of health supply chain practitioners.
- PSA also had a [Medical Waste Management Co-Creation Workshop](#) with Kisumu County and the National Environmental Management Agency (NEMA), and held a [Medical Waste Management: An Overview Of Existing Disinfection Methods Validation Workshop](#) on October 3, 2024.
- PSA contacted the International Association of Public Health Logisticians (IAPHL) during the RMIT survey to collect data on the plug & play framework tool for humanitarian organisations in waste management practices.
- Partners from the WREC project participated in the WORM workshop organised at Humanitarian and Networks and Partnerships Week 2024.
- Hanken and RMIT VN have been part of a project on medical waste ([MedView](#)) during 2024, focusing on medical waste management in healthcare facilities in Vietnam.
- Hanken is part of a Nordic network on health crises ([HealthCrisNet](#)) since 2025. To support knowledge exchange with the network, the WORM final seminar invited the co-ordinator of HealthCrisNet as a keynote speaker.
- Partners from KLU shared Deliverable D2.1 on Sustainable procurement criteria to different contact partners at humanitarian organisations including the International Committee of the Red Cross (ICRC), Save the Children, the United Nation Refugee Agency (UNHCR), and the Danish Refugee Council. The objective is to determine how these organisations can use this report to develop their sustainable procurement strategy.

- In Nairobi, Kenya on February 21, 2025, PSA [presented WORM findings](#) under the theme “Strengthening Health and Humanitarian Supply Chains in a Digital Age” at the Health and Humanitarian Logistics (HHL) Annual Conference 2025. This session focused on environmental sustainability and medical waste management and enabled cross-project learning and engagement with global humanitarian logistics networks.
- KLU participated in a panel discussion on [“Reducing the carbon and environmental footprint of procurement”](#) during HNPW 2025. This session provides participants with go-to resources on lifecycle analyses and offers a preview of findings from the joint ICRC/Climate Action Accelerator/EPFL project on LCAs of key items of the sector. Additionally, learnings from a WREC study, conducted in collaboration with KLU and CHORD, on measuring emissions in humanitarian supply chains, as well as insights from the WORM project on LCAs of bio-based materials were shared.
- On April 9, 2025, an online meeting dedicated to *GHG Emission and Waste Coordination Group Meeting* was hosted by WREC. It features insights from ICRC and KLU/CHORD on measuring emission, including results from the WORM project on the LCA of bio-based materials.
- Throughout the project, Innovasjon Norge has actively integrated the outcomes of WORM into its dialogue and capacity-building activities with projects supported by the Humanitarian Innovation Programme. They are currently supporting around [seven ongoing innovation initiatives](#) focused on humanitarian waste management. They engage with these projects at least three times per year through advisory group meetings but also through capacity building webinar and their participation in key conferences such as HNPW and RILW, where they actively disseminate insights and learning from their knowledge base.
- During the two years of the project, WORM promotion has been done at the FRC Logistic Centre trainings directed for field hospital delegates. Altogether, WORM promotion was done at five different trainings in 2024 and seven trainings in 2025. WORM’s results have informed FRC’s waste management guidelines and SOPs for field hospitals.

Apart from the above, WORM is represented at various standing committees, e.g. the Logistics Cluster’s WREC and medical logistics groups, WHO’s “Science Translation for Health Emergencies Community”, and DG ECHO’s [Humanitarian Leadership Group on Supply Chain](#) (HLGSC). Within the latter, WORM has been an integral part of the environmental sustainability and procurement workshops, feeding into its communication and policy development, as well as represented on the leadership team of the High-Level Conference on the Humanitarian Supply Chain.

Figure 34: High-Level Conference on the Humanitarian Supply Chain in Brussels

Clustering activities with the sister project

Throughout the project, close cooperation was established with the sister project "Bio4HUMAN - Identifying bio-based solutions for waste management applicable to humanitarian sector" (GA #101135144), funded under the same call. A wide range of joint activities were carried out with Bio4HUMAN, including the following:

- > **Joint kick-off meeting** on January 25, 2024.
- > Initiation and organisation of **bilateral meetings** every 2 months with the two project coordinators and communication & dissemination contact points.
- > **Mutual promotion** on social media.
- > Shared list of similar projects and initiatives we can cluster with.
- > **Cross-promotion** on each other's website with a special webpage entitled **"Our sister project"**.
- > Technical meetings and exchange of information (e.g. DG ECHO WORM/Bio4HUMAN meeting on localisation and protection session on April 16, 2024).
- > Participation of Bio4HUMAN at the WORM's General Assembly in May 2024 and at the HNPW2024 workshop.
- > **Co-organisation of a session** at the HNPW2025 titled *"Waste management in humanitarian operations: Bio-based solutions and raising awareness challenge"*.
- > Appearance of WORM in the [Bio4HUMAN' project presentation video](#) and of Bio4HUMAN in [WORM' project presentation video](#).
- > **Joint newsletter** (M12).
- > Mention of Bio4HUMAN in [WORM third newsletter](#).
- > Appearance of WORM in [Bio4HUMAN third newsletter](#).
- > Participation and presentation of Bio4HUMAN at [WORM Final event](#).
- > Mention of Bio4HUMAN in WORM's final media press kit.

Figure 35: WORM publication on LinkedIn re-sharing Bio4HUMAN results

4. EXPLOITATION

The first concrete step regarding the design of the project exploitation process covers the identification of Key Exploitable Results (KERs).

A KER is a tangible or intangible project output, whatever its form or nature, which has been deemed to be of high priority for project transfer actions: something new that comes out of the project that can be used, has value and is beneficial for the society. This result is selected and considered relevant for its high potential to be "exploited", i.e. to make use and derive benefits down the value chain of a product, process, or solution, or to serve as an important input for policy, further research or education.

In the PDCE, at M6, WORM partners proposed a preliminary table presenting the expected results of the project with potential of exploitation, as well as pathways for exploitation and dissemination. At the end of the project, this list was updated by the partners taking into consideration all the knowledge outputs developed within each WP. As a result of this process, 3 KERs have been identified. An overview of this list is available in Table 2 below.

Table 2: List of WORM key exploitable results

#	Types of result	Lead partner	Future users	Exploitation and Dissemination
KER 1	Online open-access Catalogue for bio-based solutions for humanitarian actors (and health care actors) including sustainability and technical criteria.	Solvoz	Academia, NGOs, Suppliers, Companies.	Available in open access via the WORM website. The platform enables data export in variety of formats.
KER 2	Plug-and-Play model	RMIT	Academia, NGOs, Waste management providers.	Available in open access on the WORM website.
KER 3	Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) for product use, reuse, recycling, reverse logistics and recovery in field hospitals and Emergency Medical Teams (EMTs) in humanitarian setting, as well as for donation and handover management in EMTs or field hospitals.	Hanken	EMTs, NGOs.	Available in open access on the WORM website.

4.1. KER 1 – Catalogue for biobased solutions for humanitarian actors

The Catalogue was officially launched the 8 October 2024. It offers an open-access, knowledge portal and catalogue within integrated comprehensive market assessment tool specifically designed to support humanitarian organisations, health workers, and sustainability experts. This initiative provides key stakeholders with a transparent, knowledge-driven marketplace for bio-based products and alternatives.

The Catalogue presents a unique opportunity for manufacturers, companies and other private sector entities as they can directly inform humanitarian procurement processes and play a critical role in the global push towards greener, more sustainable operations.

Figure 36: WORM Catalogue

4.2. KER 2 – Plug-and-Play model

The **Plug-and-Play model** (D4.2) was developed by the WORM consortium as part of the WP4 on “Waste management at field hospitals”. It counts as one of the five policy briefs of the project.

Deploying a field hospital is a highly complex process requiring strong coordination and a thorough understanding of the local context with regard to national requirements, infrastructure, and availability of waste management service providers. There is still a significant discrepancy between humanitarian organisations (HOs) and local waste management providers about the selection of an appropriate and desirable waste treatment approach.

The objective of the Plug-and-Play model is to provide HOs with a tool to support their decision-making process for the adoption of an appropriate waste treatment methodology that considers institutional objectives and the availability of local waste management providers. The model guides HOs in adopting suitable technologies while establishing connections with local waste management service providers, thus mitigating costly, standardised treatments. A multi-criterion decision analysis methodology was used to evaluate and compare multiple, often conflicting, criteria within the waste management decision-making process.

During the project, the team successfully designed a Plug-and-Play model that incorporates localised context settings for both Kenya and Vietnam, supporting HOs deploying within those regions. The plug and play model can be used as a starting point to understand HOs criteria and assessment of suitable technologies, service providers. It can also serve as a tool in understanding the local context to inform the HOs for further effective partnership.

4.3. KER 3 – Standard Operating Procedures for EMTs and field hospitals in humanitarian settings

The **Standard Operating Procedure (SOP)** for product use, reuse, recycling, reverse logistics and recovery in field hospitals and EMTs in humanitarian setting (D5.1) and the SOP for donation and handover management in EMTs or field hospitals (D5.2) were developed by the WORM consortium as part of the WP5 on “Recycling and waste management at field hospitals”.

Current practices of deployed field hospitals are fragmented, and the proposed SOPs bring together best practices from existing waste management SOPs, as well as the results of the WORM project. These SOPs are rooted on needs-based procurement practices that highlight efficient product and material use. They are applicable to all field hospital deployments operating in a humanitarian setting:

- The SOP for product use, reuse, recycling, reverse logistics and recovery focuses on embedding circular processes throughout. It provides operational guidance for extending equipment/product lifespan, enabling reuse and repair, recycling and repurposing non-contaminated materials, implementing recovery systems, and improving disposal methods of hazardous waste, reverse logistics and a sustainable handover process at the end of deployment. It presents operating procedures for managing waste in field hospital contexts. It draws on WORM’s procurement guidelines and technical specifications of products and materials to ensure compliance and sustainability. It also addresses barriers such as financial constraints, technical capacity gaps, and regulatory compliance, offering mitigation strategies and monitoring mechanisms.
- The SOP for donation and handover management in EMT or field hospitals establishes a structured approach for donation and handover management, ensuring continuity of waste management practices throughout EMT or field hospital deployment. It provides clear procedures, documentation templates and monitoring mechanism to support ethical, transparent and sustainable assets to local partners. Circularity principles are incorporated to prevent environmental burdens on local systems and ensure alignment with World Health Organisation’s EMT standards and national regulations. The SOP also promotes awareness on sustainable materials, appropriate waste management practices and equipment operation and maintenance.

Together, the SOPs provide a comprehensive framework for end-users regarding use, re-use, maintenance, and repair of products, materials, components within the EMT and field hospital contexts to implement circular, sustainable, and accountable practices during deployment and transition phases. They go beyond the deploying organisations by also focusing on the handover to local partners. As well as giving practical frameworks for operations, the data from deployments will feed into the strategic decisions made for future deployments. The handover SOPs highlight awareness campaigns on sustainable materials, appropriate waste management, and maintenance practices of equipment. The SOPs links field level actions to strategic decisions, enabling humanitarian actors to reduce waste, optimize resources and strengthen compliance with environmental and donor standards.

The SOPs are already being used by the intended end-users, exceeding the consortium's expectations. In particular, the Finnish Red Cross is using them at the moment for their EMT. There are also ongoing discussions about the SOPs becoming part of the World Health Organisation’s training materials.

5. IMPACT ASSESSMENT

Monitoring the impact of the different communication and dissemination activities involves a systematic collection of data and reporting of information from all partners. This information serves to deliver the final verdict on the success of the dissemination process undertaken by the project.

To measure the success of the implemented communication and dissemination activities, a detailed communication and dissemination plan was created at M6 (D7.1) in order to check that all activities are planned and are effectively taking place, integrating Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to measure the impact of each dissemination and communication activity. KPIs are a measuring factor for the performance and progress of an activity, message, task, etc. towards its expected impact. Several KPIs have been defined for each activity.

They were used throughout the project to assess the performance of dissemination activities and to adjust the dissemination plan whenever targets were not met or the expected impact was not achieved. This ongoing evaluation allowed for timely reorientation of strategies to improve effectiveness. For instance, a mid-term impact assessment was conducted and documented in the Mid-term report on communication, dissemination and exploitation (D7.3).

The table presenting the KPIs reached at M24 is available in the figure 35 below.

WORM Communication and dissemination impact assessment												
Dissemination or communication channel	Name	Purpose and expected impact	When (and where, if relevant)	Target Audience	KPI	Objective	Status of KPI - December 2025	Excellent (>100%)	Good (100%)	Moderate (<75%)	Weak (<50%)	Responsible partner
Events organised by the project	Webinars	Inform and promote about the results of the project Get support from the scientific and industrial communities Transfer of knowledge	Whole project duration	Industry, Waste management organisations	Number of webinars	2	3	>2	2	1,5	1	All partners
					Number of attendees per event	30	35	>30	30	22,5	15	
	Workshops	Inform and promote about the results of the project Get support from the scientific and industrial communities Transfer of knowledge	Whole project duration	Industry, Waste management organisations	Number of workshops	4	10	>4	4	3	2	All partners
					Number of attendees per event	20	31,9	>20	20	15	10	
	Targeted local awareness campaign	Share guidelines and recommendations Improve infrastructures & services Raise awareness about the project and its social and economic benefits	January 2025 - December 2025	Industry, Waste Management organisations, Policy and decisionmakers, Scientific community, Citizens, media	Number of campaign	2	4	>1	1	1	0	PSA
Final conference	Inform about the project and its results Highlight the efforts done to green the humanitarian sector	December 2025	All	Number of participants	100	89	>100	100	75	50	All partners	
Clustering & synergies	Joint actions	Facilitate synergies between projects and initiatives related to circular economy	Whole project duration	European and international networks & projects	Number of actions per year	2	6	>2	2	2	1	All partners
Participation in external events and conferences	Practitioner events	Transfer of knowledge Reuse of the scientific data Receive support from scientific community	Whole project duration	Humanitarian & medical organisations, Waste Management organisations	Number of events	2	10	>2	2	1	1	All partners
	Academic conferences	Promote the scientific results to interested groups and interact with stakeholders	Whole project duration	Scientific community, industry	Number of conferences	2	7	>2	2	1	1	All partners
Promotional tools	Website	Inform about the project Promote the project	Whole project duration	All	Number of views	4000	16145	>4000	4000	3000	2000	EURONOVIA
					News per year	12	25,5	>12	12	9	6	
	Social medias (LinkedIn, Twitter, Facebook)	Inform about the project Promote the project	March 2024	All	Number of followers	300	871	>300	300	225	150	EURONOVIA
					Posts per year	24	94,5	>24	24	18	12	
	Newsletters	Inform about the project Promote the project	Every 6 months - 1st issue in June 2024	All	Number of issues	4	5	>4	4	3	2	EURONOVIA
Number of subscribers	500	259	>500	500	375	250						
Practice abstracts	Inform about the project and its results Promote the project	2 batches: October 2024, August 2025	Humanitarian & medical organisations, Waste Management organisations	Number of practices identified	11	12	>11	11	8,25	5,5	All partners	
Press releases	Inform about the project and its results Promote the project	Whole project	All	Number of press releases	2	5	>2	2	1	1	EURONOVIA	
Publications	Scientific publications in journal	Inform and promote about the scientific results of the project Transfer of knowledge	Whole project duration	Scientific community, industry	Number of publications	>2	4	>2	2	1	1	All partners
	Policy brief	Inform about the project/results	Whole project duration	Policy and decisionmakers at local, national, European and international levels	Number of policy brief	5	5	>5	5	3	2	All partners
	Press media, non-scientific articles	Raise awareness about the project/results and its positive impacts and benefits for society	Whole project duration	All	Number of articles	4	11	>4	4	2	0	All partners

Figure 37: WORM communication and dissemination impact assessment

The following scale was used to score each KPI:

- If the results are lower than 50% of the target, the result is considered as Low.
- If the results are lower or equal to 75% but above 50%, the result is considered as Moderate.
- If the results are lower or equal to 100% but above 75%, the result is considered as Good.
- If the results are higher than 100%, the result is considered as High.

Over 80% of our KPIs received a 'high' score, while **95% were rated as either 'high' or 'good'** (see Table 3).

Table 3: Distribution of KPI evaluation scores

Score	High	Good	Moderate	Low
% of KPI at M12	59%	35%	0%	5%
% of KPI at M24	85%	10%	5%	0%

The activities were therefore well aligned with the work plan.

A comparison of the KPI assessment at M12 and M24 shows an increase in the 'High' category (+26%) and a complete absence of KPIs in the 'Low' category.

The **highest performing KPIs** are related to:

- The number of webinars (target: 2) and workshops (target: 3) organised by the WORM consortium as well as the number of attendees at these events (target: 30 and 20, respectively).
- The number of joint actions with projects and initiatives related to the circular economy (target: 2 per year).
- The participation in practitioner events (target: 2) and academic conferences (target: 2) to disseminate the project results.
- The number of WORM website views (target: 4 000) and the number of articles published (target: 12 per year).
- The number of followers on the WORM social media (target: 500) and the number of posts published (target: 24).
- The number of newsletters sent out to the mailing list (target: 4).
- The number of practice abstracts identified (target: 11).
- The number of press releases (target: 2).
- The number of scientific publications using the WORM results (target: >2).
- The number of non-scientific articles in the press media (target: N/A, final score of 11 articles).

These high results clearly demonstrate the **strong engagement and commitment of all consortium members** to the communication and dissemination of the WORM project.

The **'moderate' performing KPI** relates to subscribers to the project newsletter which can be explained by the fact that the target set for this activity was very high from the start for a two-year project (target: 500 subscribers to the newsletter).

Additional efforts and new actions were put in place by the consortium to increase the performance of this KPI. In the mid-term report (D7.3), we highlighted that:

- An intensive campaign to promote the newsletter subscription form was ongoing through WORM's social media. This was done to reach the numerous followers who were already interested in the project, as well as other external networks, thanks to the mobilisation of the partners.
- All attendees of WORM events were also asked if they wished to subscribe to the newsletter to keep informed of the project's progress.

Both activities proved to be effective, as evidenced by the increase in the number of subscribers, which reached a 'moderate' score.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The communication and dissemination activities have been carried out in line with the Grant Agreement and the strategy and the objectives defined in the Plan for dissemination, communication and exploitation (D7.1).

Throughout the project, all partners were actively involved in communication activities and in disseminating the project's outputs. These efforts included participating in events, writing scientific publications, liaising with the press, producing policy briefs, and preparing practice abstracts. The consortium organised a wide range of activities, from online webinars to co-creation and validation workshops, culminating in a successful final event in Helsinki in November 2025.

During the second half of the project, particular emphasis was placed on the targeted local awareness campaigns in Kenya and Vietnam. These campaigns aimed to raise awareness on improved waste management practices in specific local contexts and engaged a diverse set of stakeholders, including citizens, students, policymakers, humanitarian organisations, and local authorities.

In the final months, the consortium further strengthened project outreach by releasing the last major deliverables, notably the Causal Loop Diagrams on bio-based solutions (D6.1) and the Standard Operating Procedures for Emergency Medical Teams and field hospitals (D5.1, D5.2), producing a final brochure, a final media press kit, and maintaining a strong presence on social media.

Close collaboration among all the partners ensured impactful communication, dissemination and exploitation of WORM results, securing their long-term relevance and uptake.

ANNEX 1 – Tracking table

21	Education and training events	Local awareness campaign in Kisumu, Kenya	In celebration of World Environment Day on June 5 at Joel Omino primary school, Pamela Steele Associates (PSA) in collaboration with local artists successfully created awareness through poem and Drama performance and brochure distribution. This campaign, titled "Raising Community Awareness on proper Waste Management" aimed to promote environmental protection at the local level through raising awareness of the dangers of incineration, harmful effects of plastic and medical waste, and promote safer alternatives among others.	PSA	N/A	5/6/2025	Kisumu, Kenya	Local	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x			Number of brochures distributed	1200			Delivered	Drama and poem performance
	Education and training events	Event: "Together with Waste Collectors – Connecting Communities, Protecting the Environment" Combined with planting one hectare of mangrove forest in Nam Ninh Hoa commune, Khanh Hoa province	PSA, in collaboration with the Khanh Hoa Provincial Red Cross and the People's Committee of Nam Ninh Hoa commune, organizes the event "Together with Waste Collectors – Connecting Communities, Protecting the Environment", combined with the activity of planting one hectare of coastal mangrove forest. This is one of the key activities under the project "Research on Waste Management in Humanitarian Activities" funded by the Research Executive Agency (REA) of the European	PSA	VNRC	29/7/2025	Khanh Hoa Province, Vietnam	National			x	x	x	x	x	x	x		Number of participants	300			Delivered	[?] @ "CUNG... - Hội Chữ thập đỏ Việt Nam - Viet Nam Red Cross Society L Facebook https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1cJF_7G-6k8GsmccrO4C2Ukzlh06_4t347usp=sha ring Links to articles: https://baokhanhhoa.vn/xa-hoi/2025/07/hon-300-nguoi-qua-thu-
22	Education and training events	Local awareness campaign in Kisumu, Kenya	PSA developed mural art about dangers of incineration in 3 healthcare facilities in Kisumu county	PSA	N/A	27/05/2025	Kisumu, Kenya	Local			x	x	x	x	x			Other: Please specify in the comments				Delivered	Mural awareness	
23	Education and training events	Workshop on dangers of incinerating mixed waste	PSA hosted a virtual stakeholder workshop to further educate a broader audience on the dangers of incineration. The dialogue focused on the dangers of incinerating mixed medical waste	PSA	N/A	16/9/2025	Virtual	Local			x	x	x	x	x	x			Number of participants	37			Delivered	Link
24	Conferences	AidEX Geneva	Workshop on WORM themes at AidEX	Hanken	ICRC	22/10/2025	Geneva, Switzerland	International	x	x				x	x	x			Number of participants	20			Delivered	https://aid-expo.com/
25	Meetings	General Assembly	Final General Assembly meeting in Helsinki, Finland	Hanken	All	3/11/2025	Helsinki, Finland	International																
26	Conferences	Final WORM Seminar	Final public seminar held for WORM	Hanken	all	4/11/2025	Helsinki, Finland	International	x		x	x	x	x	x	x	x		Number of participants				Delivered	
27	Education and training events	CLD bio-based validation Workshop	Invited experts, including manufacturers and innovators, on bio-based materials and products to give feedback and validate CLD model	KLU	N/A	9/9/2025	Virtual	International	x	x					x	x			Number of participants	10			Delivered	
28	Education and training events	Toppsemi	Industry event organised with Handelsgillet and Ekonomiska Samfundet, talk on Economic growth through the green transition	Hanken	N/A	12/02/2025	Helsinki, Finland	National	x	x	x	x	x	x			x		Number of participants	100			Delivered	
29	Education and training events	GBSN changemaker	Thought provocation for future changemakers through the Global Business School Network	Hanken	N/A	25/08/2025	Virtual	International								x			Number of participants	12				
30	Other scientific collaboration	SDG week	Presentation at the sneak peek to sustainability research event	Hanken	N/A	24/09/2025	Helsinki, Finland	National								x	x		Number of participants	30				
31	Other: Please specify in comments	DG ECHO's Humanitarian Leadership Group on Supply Chain	Global alignment of humanitarian supply chains, with various donors, humanitarian organisations, and academia	Hanken	KLU	2024-2025	various	International			x	x				x	x	x	Number of participants	40				
32	Clustering activities	DG ECHO's Humanitarian Leadership Group on Supply Chain	HLGSC leadership meeting	Hanken	KLU	04/12/2024	Brussels, Belgium	International			x	x				x	x	x	Number of participants	40				
33	Clustering activities	DG ECHO's Humanitarian Leadership Group on Supply Chain	HLGSC leadership meeting	Hanken	KLU	10/12/2025	Brussels, Belgium	International			x	x				x	x	x	Number of participants	40				
34	Clustering activities	DG ECHO's Humanitarian Leadership Group on Supply Chain	HLGSC workshop on environmental sustainability	Hanken	KLU	12-13-05-2025	Lyon, France	International			x	x				x	x	x	Number of participants	60				
35	Clustering activities	DG ECHO's Humanitarian Leadership Group on Supply Chain	HLGSC workshop on procurement	Hanken	KLU	13-14-05-2025	Lyon, France	International			x	x				x	x	x	Number of participants	60				
36	Clustering activities	DG ECHO's Humanitarian Leadership Group on Supply Chain	HLGSC workshop on digitalisation	Hanken	KLU	1-2-07-2025	Geneva, Switzerland	International			x	x				x	x	x	Number of participants	60				

37	Clustering activities	DG ECHO's Humanitarian Leadership Group on Supply Chain	HLGSC workshop on preparedness	Hanken	KLU	30-09-01-10-2025	Copenhagen, Denmark	International			x	x					x	x	x	x		Number of participants	60				
38	Clustering activities	DG ECHO's Humanitarian Leadership Group on Supply Chain	HLGSC workshop on localisation	Hanken	KLU	29-30-09-2025	Copenhagen, Denmark	International			x	x					x	x	x	x		Number of participants	60				

Please update this table with the list of your publications where the project results are presented. Always write in the last row.

	Type of scientific publication	Title of the scientific publication	Type of PID (repository)	PID of deposited publication	Authors (leading partners)	Title of the journal or equivalent	ISSN/eISSN	Publisher	Month & Year of publication	Peer-reviewed?	Open access through the repository at the time of publication?	Did you charge OA publishing fees to the project?
1	Chapters in books	Humanitarian supply chains: challenging the system	DOI	https://doi.org/10.4337/9781803924922	Gyöngyi Kovács (Hanken)	The Supply Chain: A System in Crisis	9781803924922	Iward Elgar Publishi	April 2024		No	No
2	Conference proceeding	Integrating healthcare waste management in disaster risk reduction strategies			Margot Rocheteau, Sa	EurOMA 2025 Conference (theme: Operations Management opening to m			juin-25		No	No
3	Conference proceeding	Bio-based products in humanitarian medical supply chains: supply market intelligence and life cycle assessment			Virva Tuomala, Sarah J	EurOMA 2025 Conference (theme: Operations Management opening to m			juli-25		No	No
4	Conference proceeding	MEDICAL WASTE MANAGEMENT: APPLICATION OF CIRCULAR ECONOMY PRINCIPLES IN A DEVELOPING COUNTRY CONTEXT			Virva Tuomala, Sarah J	NOFOMA 2024			juin-24	Yes	No	No

worm

Waste in humanitarian Operations:
Reduction and Minimisation

Funded by the
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